

DIDACTIC FEATURES OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' SPEECH

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Annotation: The article is aimed at revealing the didactic features of improving the methodological preparation of future primary teachers to develop students' speech, the importance of innovative approaches aimed at familiarizing future primary teachers with new modern technologies in the higher education system.

Keywords: didactic, didactic factors, principles, methodological preparation, primary school, educational methods, formation of teaching forms

Introduction. The issue of training highly qualified specialists in our republic is being considered at the level of state policy. In particular, the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" sets out the top priorities for improving the quality of education [1]. Based on this historical document, the most important tasks facing today's specialists and researchers are to develop the methodological training of future primary school teachers, expand the scope of scientific research aimed at this goal and increase their effectiveness, and develop new pedagogical conditions aimed at developing the methodological training of teachers. One of the main tasks of modern education is to create a creative environment for each student to develop their abilities, inner capabilities, and creative potential, thereby creating a child with the skills to independently acquire and assimilate knowledge. The ability to independently solve educational and training problems related to the tasks to be performed, to plan tasks to achieve the set goal, and to achieve the mastery of such virtues are tasks consistent with the above-mentioned main goals. Among the important tasks to be carried out in this direction, one of the priority tasks was to form the specialists being trained from a scientific point of view, to educate and bring up a well-rounded person who is spiritually and morally mature, has an independent worldview, thinks creatively, and is committed to national values.

How can the laws of knowledge be used in the educational process? For this, it is necessary to adhere to didactic principles. This is the methodological basis of the perceived didactic laws; this is knowledge about the purpose, essence, content, structure of education in a form that does not prevent its use as a

permanent standard of practice. They serve as a methodological basis that guides the choice of content, forms, methods and means of education.

When improving methodological training, these principles direct the teacher to operate on the basis of a conscious, systematic, reflective and innovative approach. We would like to dwell on the main didactic principles used in our research and their analysis.

The principle of scientificity - ensures that the educational process is organized on the basis of theoretical foundations, scientific approaches, linguistics and methodological concepts. The future teacher deeply masters the scientific foundations of the subject. Learns to interpret the lesson material scientifically correctly and consistently. Methodological decisions (choice of method, evaluation criteria) are based on scientific criteria.

The principle of demonstrativeness - involves conveying the studied language material and speech activity to the student and pupil through visual, audio, kinesthetic means. Forms a strategy for using real objects, schemes, animations, video lessons in lessons. Ya.A. Komensky in his "Great Didactics" justified demonstrativeness as a natural and effective way of education.

The principle of systematization, continuity - all parts of education are interconnected, purposeful, organized in logical sequence. Lesson plans, summaries, technological maps are drawn up on the basis of a systematic approach. The skill of students to gradually form their speech develops. The teacher plans, monitors and improves his pedagogical activity.

The principle of axiological and independence - a modern axiological approach requires working with the internal values of the individual. Independence implies the formation of the future teacher's ability to develop methodological materials, assignments, lesson plans, as a creative and thinking subject.

Thus, the laws of the theory of teaching in a higher educational institution correspond to the system of didactic principles, which participate as the basic rules necessary for organizing and planning the educational process. In substantiating the principles of teaching, higher education didactics provides for the following: the purpose of teaching in accordance with the requirements of society; objective laws of teaching; specific conditions for the educational process.

Philosophical concepts such as general and particular, essence and phenomenon, contradiction, connection are also important for didactics. Among the general-scientific concepts used in didactics, such concepts as "system", "structure", "task", "element" occupy a special place.

Didactic concepts specific to pedagogy include: education, lesson, skills, qualifications, knowledge acquisition, educational process, subject, educational methods, educational tools, educational goals, etc. [3]. There are various approaches to justifying the principles of teaching in higher education institutions. They are: bringing educational work closer to scientific work; ensuring high activity of students in independent educational and cognitive activities [2].

“Didactics is a theory of education that studies the content, methods, forms and results of the educational process. From this definition, it can be concluded that the role of didactics in improving the methodological preparation of teachers is of high importance. Didactic knowledge helps future teachers in planning lessons, applying educational methods and monitoring students' knowledge. Based on the ideas of scientists who have conducted research on the theory and history of pedagogy, the connection between didactics and methodological preparation is explained as follows: “A high level of scientific and methodological preparation is intended to achieve a high professional culture.” This shows that the methodological preparation of future teachers is based on didactic knowledge and, through this, their methodological preparation is improved. Because didactics determines the content, methods, forms and results of the educational process studies, which is a key factor in improving the methodological preparation of future teachers. In the theory of education, the didactic concepts of Ya.A. Komensky and I.F. Gerbart are of great importance.

The creation of the traditional didactic system is associated with the name of the German philosopher, psychologist and educator I.F. Gerbart (1776-1841). He critically refounded the traditional system of classes of Ya.A. Komensky and created an educational system based on the theoretical achievements of ethics and psychology [4]. As I.F. Gerbart noted, the main features of the educational system are: ensuring the intellectual development of students is the main task of the school; raising a child is the task of the family [5].

In the 50s of the 20th century, psychologist and educator B. Skinner put forward the idea of achieving efficiency in mastering the material based on the delivery of information in parts and regular monitoring of this process. This idea was later called "programmed education". Later, he created branched programs that offer the learner various materials for independent work, depending on the results of the control[6]. A higher educational institution is characterized by such circumstances as the personal development of future primary school teachers, the orientation of their interests in their profession, the stabilization of

their independent thinking, activity, and the formation of their worldview and needs for self-education. For a future teacher, student, the process of receiving education in a higher educational institution is the most important period for the formation, development, and self-improvement of qualities, knowledge, skills, and competencies that are considered professionally important for the successful implementation of pedagogical activities.

List of published works:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "2022-2026-yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida" 2022 yil 28 yanvardagi PF-60-son farmoni. 28.01.2022.
2. Лернер И.Я. Развитие мышления учащихся в процессе обучения истории: пособие для учителей. М. : Просвещение, 1992. 191 с.
3. Filin F.P. Some words about language norm and speech culture. Speech culture questions.- No7, 2006; C.44-48.
4. Kharaev Zh.A. Level of cognitive activity. Kazakhstan school, 2004. No3; 67-69.
5. Luria A.R., Yudovich, F.A. Speech and development of mental processes of the child. Moscow: Pedagogika, 2008.
6. Salnikova T.P. Methods of teaching grammar, spelling and speech development, M., 2001.

